

THE MOTIVE OF DEATH IN THE STORY OF LEV NIKOLAEVICH TOLSTOY "THE DEATH OF IVAN ILYICH"

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Abstract: The article presents an analysis of the motive of life and death in the story “The Death of Ivan Ilyich”, and examines the features of creating an artistic image of the main character - Ivan Ilyich.

Key words: Lev Nikolaevich Tolstoy, death, soul, self-knowledge, indifference, greed, Ivan Ilyich

Count Lev Nikolaevich Tolstoy (1828-1910) is an outstanding Russian writer, publicist, thinker, one of the greatest romanticists in world literature, who wrote quite a few works and novels that are currently famous not only in Russia, but also abroad. And each of his works has its own special, deep meaning. In such works as “Childhood”, “War and Peace”, “Anna Karenina”, “The Death of Ivan Ilyich”, philosophical themes about the meaning of life and death are touched upon, and his works also show the peculiarities of the national character of the Russian person. «National cultures we can identify common personality structures and elements that provide forms of worldview, perception, thinking and behavior common to all of them. It is the personality and behavioral qualities that distinguish members of one national group from representatives of other groups» [4, p.95].

In works like “The Death of Ivan Ilyich”, from the first seconds of reading the title, you can put forward a hypothesis that the work will be about life and death. The story begins with an epilogue, where Ivan Ilyich’s colleagues and friends learn about his death from the newspaper: “Gentlemen! - he said, “Ivan Ilyich - that he died” [1, p. 94]. Instead of experiencing grief, compassion, and thinking about their own inevitable end, people are only glad that this did not happen to them.

Tracing the thoughts and feelings of a terminally ill official, Tolstoy shows how a man runs away from thoughts of death and how death leads him to understand what his life was.

But the author reveals not only philosophical thoughts and spiritual awareness, but also the author tries to show how hypocritical, greedy people can be, and are ready to go over their heads just to get what they want.

“The place remained with him, but there was a consideration that in the event of his death, Alekseev could be appointed in his place, and in Alekseev’s place either Vinnikov or Shtabel could be appointed. So, having heard about the death of Ivan Ilyich, the first thought of each of the gentlemen gathered in the office was about what significance this death could have on the transfers or promotions of the members themselves or their acquaintances. “...” Now I’ll probably get the place of Stabel or Vinnikov, thought Fyodor Vasilyevich. “This was promised to me long ago, and this increase amounts to an increase of eight hundred rubles for me, in addition to the office. “...” I will now have to ask for the transfer of my brother-in-law from Kaluga, - Petor Ivanovich. - My wife will be very happy. Now it will no longer be possible to say that I never did anything for her family” [1, p. 102-108].

Understanding and joy that it was not you who died, but someone else, and you are still alive and well: “What is it like, he died, but I didn’t” [1, p. 106], - everyone thought or felt. Close acquaintances, the so-called friends of Ivan Ilyich,

at the same time involuntarily say that now they need to fulfill very boring duties of decency and go to the memorial service and pay a condolence visit to the widow. “Pyotr Ivanovich’s comrade, Schwartz, came down from above and, seeing him coming in from the top step, stopped and winked at him, as if saying: “Ivan Ilyich made a stupid decision: what’s wrong with you and me” [1, p. 109]

The main character Ivan Ilyich is a nobleman, an ordinary person, protected from himself by his ordinary life. From childhood, this hero was well brought up, fair and gentle in his state affairs, but life in the bureaucracy and aristocratic communication along this path gradually subordinated him to the state of life in his own circle.

The image of Ivan Ilyich is not contradictory, but also not one-sided, it is not a “flat” character with one dominant trait, not an obviously negative character, but an image of a person similar to other people, “like everyone else.” Tolstoy repeatedly emphasized this similarity, the similarity of Ivan Ilyich’s life to the lives of other people: “The past history of Ivan Ilyich’s life was the simplest and most ordinary” [1, p. 95].

In his work, Tolstoy managed to reflect the real experience of death in both the physical and psychological aspects. And so, in order to show the approaching death of the main character, the author describes physical changes in him: “He has a strange taste and something awkward in the left side of his stomach” [1, p. 98], but over time the pain worsened and the condition became more and more unstable. In the story, Tolstoy writes many times about his sensations in his stomach and mouth, and this is what shows us how the main character gradually takes steps towards death. Moreover, Ivan Ilyich heard his wife’s conversation with his brother-in-law, who said that he was now like a dead man, and there was not a ray of light in his eyes. These details are not embellished, simple, but expressive and realistically convey the gradual changes in Ivan Ilyich’s body as

death approaches. This is where Tolstoy's genius lies: his ability to present characters and situations through realistic and simple descriptions.

Due to the illness, not only his physical health deteriorates, but his psychological health is also undermined, which Tolstoy portrayed very accurately, for example, it happens that Ivan Ilyich complains that the food is not tasty, then his son is not sitting correctly at the table, or My daughter's hairstyle doesn't suit her face. Every day he becomes more and more grumpy and dissatisfied with everything that happens around him. And it is here that you can see that the disease turned him into someone who was offended by everyone around him and extremely wounded; every time he noticed pity towards him, he affirmed even more in his heart that he was hopelessly ill.

Tolstoy is infinitely attentive to the very process of dying - the slow change in sensations, the reassessment of values, the restructuring of the picture of the world. All these changes can be reduced to one denominator: the approach of death pulls a person out of everyday, semi-automatic existence, forces him to re-see himself, those around him and his own life, and face the final truths of existence. Not only death itself is understood as an awakening, even approaching death turns out to be a kind of awakening from the “sleep of life.” Like Natasha Rostova in the opera (a textbook example of detachment), the dying Ivan Ilyich ceases to understand what previously seemed obvious, feels his own body as someone else's, feels the lies and falsity of his usual way of life. In this sense, dying and impending death is the most radical withdrawal of which a person is capable.

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